

Report on the second Delphi study

DELPHI STUDY REPORT

Contents

1. Delphi study plan	3
The aim of the research.....	Error! Bookmark not defined.
Research instrument.....	Error! Bookmark not defined.
2. First round Delphi study results	9
3. Second round Delphi study questionnaire	9
4. Needs analysis questionnaire	16
Literature review.....	Error! Bookmark not defined.

1. Delphi study plan

The aim of the research

The goal of conducting the Delphi study is to gain a deeper insight into the Sustainable entrepreneurship and Sustainability Reporting, in order to, through the proposal of a training program, encourage the development of these skills, which will make it easier for young people to successfully enter the work sphere when hiring or starting their own business.

Sustainable entrepreneurship and innovation have been getting more and more attention, so the USE IPM aims at encouraging entrepreneurship focused on sustainability, and creating innovative solutions that respect a three-norms framework: doing good, avoiding harm, and protecting both, the society and the planet. Sustainability justification can be provided based on sustainability reporting and therefore, sustainability reporting is considered as very important task for every business entity.

In this sense, the following are the specific objectives of the research:

1. Identification of environmental aspects of sustainability,
2. Identification of economic aspects of sustainability,
3. Identification of social aspects of sustainability,
4. Identification of sustainability aspects that have to be improved in widening countries,
5. Identification of circular economy actions, especially the ones that can be implemented in widening countries,
6. Identification of sustainability reporting presence in widening countries.

Research tasks

Considering the defined goal of the research, the implementation of the Delphi study should answer several key tasks:

1. Identifying environmental, economic and social aspects of sustainability,
2. Identifying the discrepancy between those three aspects of sustainability,
3. Identifying lagging sustainability area for widening countries,
4. Identifying potentials for circular economy development,
5. Identifying the potentials and limitations for sustainability reporting.

Methodological framework of the Delphi study

Data collection and processing methods

The Delphi method is used to systematically combine the opinions of experts to reach a consensus of an informed competent group on a complex problem. This method is used to develop different alternatives, to explore or discover underlying assumptions, and to obtain consensus among domain experts on the subject of the Delphi study. It is also applicable to topics where there is controversy, debate or lack of clarity and an acceptable substitute for direct empirical evidence when the latter is unavailable. The advantages of this method are:

1. direct confrontation between experts is avoided, it does not require proximity or a face-to-face meeting of all panel participants, in one place and at the same time, which enables the independent opinion of experts, therefore there are fewer opportunities to obey the dominant opinion;
2. enables anonymity, which encourages creativity, honesty and balanced consideration of ideas;
3. increases the existing knowledge of experts in the field of research through feedback given during iterations;
4. experts contribute to the understanding and solving of important problems, communication is freed from time constraints, money is saved because there are no travel expenses, etc.;
5. methodological qualities such as confidentiality, comprehensibility and holism in terms of knowledge about the phenomenon and its context are ensured.

As the Delphi method dictates, the experts are guaranteed anonymity, and only the researcher who conducts the interviews is aware of their profile. The criteria that experts would have to meet are:

- Minimum higher education,
- Management position in the organization,
- A minimum of five years of work experience in general or a minimum of two years of experience at managerial position, or
- minimum 3 years of experience in running your own business.

Experts, participants of the Delphi study, sign the Consent for participation in the research.

Research instrument

The research instrument is the Questionnaire for experts, in the first and second round of research.

The first round of empirical research – a questionnaire for experts for an in-depth interview

Research Objective (RO)	Question
n/a	Introduce yourself and briefly explain your experience in suitability activities and/or running your own business.
RO1	Can you define the environmental aspects of sustainability?*
RO 1	How would you define and specify the environmental aspects of sustainability (at least five)?
RO2	Can you define the economic aspects of sustainability?*
RO 2	How would you define and specify the economic aspects of sustainability (at least five)?
RO3	Can you define the social aspects of sustainability?*
RO 3	How would you define and specify the social aspects of sustainability (at least five)?
RO 4	Which of these three sustainability aspects you believe is the least developed in your country and why?
RO4	What are the challenges of implementing sustainable practices in your country?
RO4	Do you believe that sustainable practices offer benefits to your business?*
RO4	If YES, list at least 5 benefits from implementing sustainable practices.
RO4	Do you implement any sustainable practices in your company?*
RO4	If YES, please list sustainable practices implemented in your company.
RO4	What drives sustainability action within your company? List all drivers that you can think of.
RO4	How can IT be used to support sustainability aspects?
RO4	Have you noticed any disruption in your business activity caused by environmental damage or climate changes? Which one?
RO5	What circular economy actions and innovation potentials can you mention as the ones that can be applied in your country?
RO6	Do you apply sustainability reporting in your company?*

USE IPM

RO6	What are potentials and limitations for sustainability reporting?
-----	---

* Respondents answer these questions with "YES" and "NO". For other questions, the respondents give at least 5 answers. For these questions, in the process of summarizing the results, the answers "YES" and answers "NO" should be counted. For other questions, all answers given by all respondents should be included in the list of offered answers, in order to create a list of answers.

After receiving the answers given by the respondents, their summarization follows, first at the level of each country, and then at the project level (the coordinators of each partner send summary answers to the questions to the project coordinator, and the coordinator summarizes them at the project level). The summary answers are the basis for creating a questionnaire for experts for the second round of research.

Coordinators by country deliver precisely defined statistics for each of the questions, namely:

1. Percentage of answers YES/NO and that 1st question under a), 2nd question under and 9th question,
2. Summarized list (5 answers per expert, but in the final list all listed with the number of citations in order to identify the key ones by the number of citations. BUT in the second round, ALL the listed sustainability aspects and practices are listed in order to obtain quantitative results, because then the number of citations is not important, but the grade from 1 to 5 - the average grade for each of the listed sustainability aspects and practices is calculated at the end, depending on the question).

Second round of empirical research – questionnaire for experts

Based on the analysis of qualitative data obtained in the first round of empirical research, i.e. through in-depth interviews, but also on the basis of a previously prepared systematic literature review, an instrument is developed for the second round of research in the form of a questionnaire. The questionnaire was distributed to experts with the aim of reaching agreement on the key soft skills needed either for starting one's own business, or for a positive evaluation by the HRM department in the selection process.

For each question that involves enumerating the answers, the experts declare themselves with grades from 1 to 5, using a Likert scale, whereby the experts are explained the grades according to the following meaning of the grade:

- 1 – Unnecessary,
- 2 - Completely insignificant,

- 3 – Partially significant,
- 4 – Significantly,
- 5 – Very significant.

Conclusion of the research using the Delphi study

The data collected in the second round are statistically processed. If more than 70% of the experts rated the offered answer as significant or very significant, it is considered that a consensus has been reached.

Then, that skill/reason for development/how to build and strengthen/prerequisite (by question) qualifies to **go into the quantitative questionnaire**. This Questionnaire is the basis of empirical research on a sample of at least 100 units (in all 4 countries), in order to identify the needs of organizations in these countries when it comes to "soft" skills.

By comparing the results of the Delphi study, focus groups and the needs analysis of organizations, a realistic picture will be created of the importance and need for the development of certain "soft" skills among young people.

Sample research

The plan is to conduct a Delphi study with experts in the field of sustainability and sustainability reporting, regardless the company size, including the experts from consulting agencies and NGOs.

The characteristics of the respondents refer to:

Field of work: At least two respondents are experts in the field of sustainability. At least two respondents are from the field of environment protection.

Work experience: All respondents have at least five years of work experience.

Profession: The respondents have different professions and formal education in different fields.

Experience: Respondents from the field of sustainability have significant experience in implementing sustainability practices. Respondents from the field of environment protection are persons who have experience in standardization (for example, introducing the ISO 14000 standard).

Gender: Respondents are members of both genders.

Resources

For the implementation of the Delphi study, two implementers are foreseen, for each partner: a moderator and an associate who will record the answers and opinions of the respondents, as well as the common conclusions that will be reached.

An in-depth interview can be conducted face-to-face or via telephone or some form of online video streaming communication.

Time

The estimated duration of the conversation with each expert is 30 minutes.

Deadlines

The planned date for the realization of the first round of the Delphi study is from February 26th till March 5th, 2024. The processing of collected data and the creation of questionnaires for the second round is planned for the period from March 6th till 7th, 2024. Data collection by distributing questionnaires in the second round of the Delphi study is planned for the period March 8th till 17th, 2024. The questionnaires should be sent to the experts who participated in the first round of the Delphi study. The analysis of the collected data and the compilation of the Report on the conducted Delphi study must be completed by March 31st, 2024.

2. First round Delphi study results

After receiving the answers given by the respondents, their summarization follows, first at the level of each country, and then at the project level (the coordinators of each partner send summary answers to the questions to the project coordinator, and the coordinator summarizes them at the project level). The summary answers are the basis for creating a questionnaire for experts for the second round of research.

Coordinators by country deliver precisely defined statistics for each of the questions, namely:

3. Percentage of answers YES/NO and that 1st question under a), 2nd and 9th question,
4. Summarized list (5 answers per expert, but in the final list all listed with the number of citations in order to identify the key ones by the number of citations.

1. More than 90% of experts said that they can define ecological (environmental), economic, but also social (societal) aspects of sustainability. Similarly, more than 90% of experts stated that sustainable practices offer benefits for your company, but also that they implement sustainable practices in their companies.

2. The most frequent answers concerning other research questions are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Delphi study – answers systematized based on first round of interviews

DELPHI STUDY REPORT	
1. Can you define the ecological (environmental) aspects of sustainability?	YES
2. How would you define and identify the ecological (environmental) aspects of sustainability (list at least five	

USE IPM

aspects)?	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Energy management2. Energy efficiency3. Pollution control4. Waste management5. Protection of biodiversity
3. Can you define the economic aspects of sustainability?	YES
4. How would you define and identify the economic aspects of sustainability (list at least five aspects)?	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Training for the education of workers2. Cooperation with stakeholders3. Transparency in reporting4. Economic growth5. Socially responsible business practices
5. Can you define the social (societal) aspects of sustainability?	YES
6. How would you define and identify the social (societal) aspects of sustainability (list at least five aspects)?	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Employee training2. Increasing awareness of waste classification3. Social inclusion4. Work conditions and health at work5. Community engagement
7. Which of the three aspects of sustainability (environmental, economic, social) do you think is the least developed in your country and why?	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Economic2. Government initiative3. Education4. Environmental5. Legal regulations
8. What are the challenges/difficulties in implementing sustainable practices in your country (list at least five challenges)?	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Investment in human resources2. Transparency of business3. Lack of resources4. Legislation5. Low level of public awareness
9. Do you believe that sustainable practices offer benefits for your company (if you are from a civil society organization or consulting firm, answer in general for companies in your country)?	YES
10. If "Yes", list at least 5 benefits of implementing sustainable practices.	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Social benefits2. Infrastructure development3. Cooperation with the community4. Resource optimization5. Cost reduction
11. Do you implement any sustainable practices in your company (if you are from a civil society organization or consulting firm, answer in general for companies in your country)?	

USE IPM

YES

12. If "Yes", please list sustainable practices implemented in your company / if you are from a civil society organization or a consulting firm, direct the answer generally towards companies in your country (list at least five practices)?

- 1. Energy efficiency**
- 2. Water management systems**
- 3. Promotion of sustainable investment**
- 4. Transparency, communication and reporting to stakeholders**
- 5. Promotion and education**

13. What drives sustainability action in your company (if you are from a civil society organization or a consulting firm, answer in general for companies in your country)? List all the drivers you can think of (list at least five)!

- 1. Strategies**
- 2. Waste management plan**
- 3. Partnerships and networks**
- 4. Financial motivation**
- 5. Satisfied employees**

14. How can IT be used to support sustainability (list at least five ways)?

- 1. Transparency in work**
- 2. Education of employees**
- 3. Digitalization and data sharing**
- 4. Communication efficiency**
- 5. information**

15. Have you noticed a disruption in your business activity caused by environmental damage or climate change (if you are from a civil organization or a consulting firm, answer in general for companies in your country)? Which disruptions?

No

16. Which circular economy actions and innovation potentials can be applied in your country (list at least five)?

- 1. Better management of all types of waste**
- 2. Digitalization of processes in all sectors**
- 3. Innovative solutions for water resource management**
- 4. Promotion of production with less waste**
- 5. Collaboration among government institutions, businesses, professionals and citizens**

17. Do you apply sustainability reporting in your company (if you are from a civil society organization or a consulting firm, answer in general for companies in your country)?

Yes

18. What are the opportunities and limitations associated with sustainability reporting (list at least five)?

Opportunities:

- 1. Stakeholder engagement and trust building**
- 2. Learning and improvement**
- 3. Increasing competitiveness**
- 4. Access to credit lines**
- 5. Long term value creation**

Limitations:

- 1. Lack of reporting knowledge**
- 2. Lack of support programs**
- 3. Lack of prescribed legal and other regulations**
- 4. Lack of standardization**
- 5. Complexity and reporting burden**

3. Second round Delphi study questionnaire

Based on the analysis of qualitative data obtained in the first round of empirical research, i.e. through in-depth interviews, but also on the basis of a previously prepared systematic literature review, an instrument is developed for the second round of research in the form of a questionnaire. The questionnaire was distributed to experts with the aim of reaching agreement on the key soft skills needed either for starting one's own business, or for a positive evaluation by the HRM department in the selection process.

For each question that involves enumerating the answers, the experts declare themselves with grades from 1 to 5, using a Likert scale, whereby the experts are given an explanation of the grades according to the following meaning of the grade:

- 1 – Completely insignificant,
- 2 – Insignificant,
- 3 – Partially significant,
- 4 – Significant,
- 5 – Very significant.

Table 3. QUESTIONNAIRE FOR EXPERTS

Dear Sir/Madam, we hereby invite you to participate in the second round of Delphi study. If you have questions related to the research, you can contact the researchers via the email address: useipmproject@gmail.com. Mark the answers that express your opinion about the following statements.

Question	Answers				
	1 - Completely insignificant	2 - Insignificant	3 - Partially significant	4 - Significant	5 - Very significant
1. To what extent are significant the following ecological (environmental) aspects of sustainability?					
a) Energy management	1	2	3	4	5
b) Energy efficiency	1	2	3	4	5
c) Pollution control	1	2	3	4	5
d) Waste management	1	2	3	4	5
e) Protection of biodiversity	1	2	3	4	5
2. To what extent are significant the following economic aspects of sustainability (list at least five aspects)?					
a) Training for the education of workers	1	2	3	4	5
b) Cooperation with stakeholders	1	2	3	4	5
c) Transparency in reporting	1	2	3	4	5
d) Economic growth	1	2	3	4	5
e) Socially responsible business practices	1	2	3	4	5
3. To what extent are significant the following social (societal) aspects of sustainability (list at least five aspects)?					
a) Employee training	1	2	3	4	5
b) Increasing awareness of waste classification	1	2	3	4	5
c) Social inclusion	1	2	3	4	5
d) Work conditions and health at work	1	2	3	4	5
e) Community engagement	1	2	3	4	5

USE IPM

4. To what extent are significant the following challenges/difficulties in implementing sustainable practices in your country (list at least five challenges)?	1 - Completely insignificant	2 - Insignificant	3 - Partially significant	4 - Significant	5 - Very significant
a) Investment in human resources	1	2	3	4	5
b) Transparency of business	1	2	3	4	5
c) Lack of resources	1	2	3	4	5
d) Legislation	1	2	3	4	5
e) Low level of public awareness	1	2	3	4	5
5. To what extent are significant the following benefits of implementing sustainable practices.	1 - Completely insignificant	2 - Insignificant	3 - Partially significant	4 - Significant	5 - Very significant
a) Social benefits	1	2	3	4	5
b) Infrastructure development	1	2	3	4	5
c) Cooperation with the community	1	2	3	4	5
d) Resource optimization	1	2	3	4	5
e) Cost reduction	1	2	3	4	5
6. To what extent are significant the following sustainable practices implemented in your company / земљи?	1	2	3	4	5
a) Energy efficiency	1	2	3	4	5
b) Water management systems	1	2	3	4	5
c) Promotion of sustainable investment	1	2	3	4	5
d) Transparency, communication and reporting to stakeholders	1	2	3	4	5
e) Promotion and education	1	2	3	4	5
7. To what extent are significant the following drivers of sustainability activities in your company/земљи?	1 - Completely insignificant	2 - Insignificant	3 - Partially significant	4 - Significant	5 - Very significant
a) Strategies	1	2	3	4	5
b) Waste management plan	1	2	3	4	5
c) Partnerships and networks	1	2	3	4	5
d) Financial motivation	1	2	3	4	5
e) Satisfied employees	1	2	3	4	5
8. To what extent is significant IT support for the following sustainability aspects?	1 - Completely insignificant	2 - Insignificant	3 - Partially significant	4 - Significant	5 - Very significant
a) Transparency in work	1	2	3	4	5
b) Education of employees	1	2	3	4	5
c) Digitalization and data sharing	1	2	3	4	5
d) Communication efficiency	1	2	3	4	5
e) Sharing information	1	2	3	4	5
9. To what extent are significant the following circular economy activities koje can be applied in your country?	1 - Completely insignificant	2 - Insignificant	3 - Partially significant	4 - Significant	5 - Very significant
a) Better management of all types of waste	1	2	3	4	5
b) Digitalization of processes in all sectors	1	2	3	4	5
c) Innovative solutions for water resource management	1	2	3	4	5
d) Promotion of production with less waste	1	2	3	4	5
e) Collaboration among government institutions, businesses, professionals and citizens	1	2	3	4	5
10. To what extent are significant the following opportunities and limitations associated with sustainability reporting?	1 - Completely insignificant	2 - Insignificant	3 - Partially significant	4 - Significant	5 - Very significant
Opportunities:					
a) Stakeholder engagement and trust building	1	2	3	4	5

USE IPM

b) Learning and improvement	1	2	3	4	5
c) Increasing competitiveness	1	2	3	4	5
d) Access to credit lines	1	2	3	4	5
e) Long term value creation	1	2	3	4	5
Limitations:	1	2	3	4	5
a) Lack of reporting knowledge	1	2	3	4	5
b) Lack of support programs					
c) Lack of prescribed legal and other regulations	1	2	3	4	5
d) Lack of standardization	1	2	3	4	5
e) Complexity and reporting burden	1	2	3	4	5

THANK YOU!

USE IPM

The data collected in the second round are statistically processed. If more than 70% of the experts rated the offered answer as significant or very significant, it is considered that a consensus has been reached. The calculation is presented in Table 3a.

Then, that claim qualifies to go into the quantitative questionnaire. This Questionnaire is the basis of empirical research on a sample of at least 100 units (in all 4 countries), in order to identify the needs and opportunities of organizations in these countries when it comes to sustainability and sustainability reporting.

4. Needs analysis questionnaire

Based on the relative score, calculated in the Table 3, the decision has been made on options that do not deserve to have place in the final questionnaire, which will be used for Needs analysis. The modifications are needed for questions 1, 2a, 3, 5.1, 5.2 and 9a.

Question	Answers				
	1 - Completely insignificant	2 - Insignificant	3 - Partially significant	4 - Significant	5 - Very significant
1. To what extent are significant the following ecological (environmental) aspects of sustainability?					
f) Energy management	1	2	3	4	5
g) Energy efficiency	1	2	3	4	5
h) Pollution control	1	2	3	4	5
i) Waste management	1	2	3	4	5
j) Protection of biodiversity	1	2	3	4	5
2. To what extent are significant the following economic aspects of sustainability (list at least five aspects)?	1 - Completely insignificant	2 - Insignificant	3 - Partially significant	4 - Significant	5 - Very significant
f) Training for the education of workers	1	2	3	4	5
g) Cooperation with stakeholders	1	2	3	4	5
h) Transparency in reporting	1	2	3	4	5
i) Economic growth	1	2	3	4	5
j) Socially responsible business practices	1	2	3	4	5
3. To what extent are significant the following social (societal) aspects of sustainability (list at least five aspects)?	1 - Completely insignificant	2 - Insignificant	3 - Partially significant	4 - Significant	5 - Very significant
f) Employee training	1	2	3	4	5
g) Increasing awareness of waste classification	1	2	3	4	5
h) Social inclusion	1	2	3	4	5
i) Work conditions and health at work	1	2	3	4	5
j) Community engagement	1	2	3	4	5
4. To what extent are significant the following challenges/difficulties in implementing sustainable practices in your country (list at least five challenges)?	1 - Completely insignificant	2 - Insignificant	3 - Partially significant	4 - Significant	5 - Very significant
f) Investment in human resources	1	2	3	4	5
g) Transparency of business	1	2	3	4	5
h) Lack of resources	1	2	3	4	5
i) Legislation	1	2	3	4	5
j) Low level of public awareness	1	2	3	4	5
5. To what extent are significant the following benefits of implementing sustainable practices.	1 - Completely insignificant	2 - Insignificant	3 - Partially significant	4 - Significant	5 - Very significant
f) Social benefits	1	2	3	4	5
g) Infrastructure development	1	2	3	4	5

USE IPM

h) Cooperation with the community	1	2	3	4	5
i) Resource optimization	1	2	3	4	5
j) Cost reduction	1	2	3	4	5
6. To what extent are significant the following sustainable practices implemented in your company / земљи?	1	2	3	4	5
f) Energy efficiency	1	2	3	4	5
g) Water management systems	1	2	3	4	5
h) Promotion of sustainable investment	1	2	3	4	5
i) Transparency, communication and reporting to stakeholders	1	2	3	4	5
j) Promotion and education	1	2	3	4	5
7. To what extent are significant the following drivers of sustainability activities in your company/земљи?	1 - Completely insignificant	2 - Insignificant	3 - Partially significant	4 - Significant	5 - Very significant
f) Strategies	1	2	3	4	5
g) Waste management plan	1	2	3	4	5
h) Partnerships and networks	1	2	3	4	5
i) Financial motivation	1	2	3	4	5
j) Satisfied employees	1	2	3	4	5
8. To what extent is significant IT support for the following sustainability aspects?	1 - Completely insignificant	2 - Insignificant	3 - Partially significant	4 - Significant	5 - Very significant
f) Transparency in work	1	2	3	4	5
g) Education of employees	1	2	3	4	5
h) Digitalization and data sharing	1	2	3	4	5
i) Communication efficiency	1	2	3	4	5
j) Sharing information	1	2	3	4	5
9. To what extent are significant the following circular economy activities koje can be applied in your country?	1 - Completely insignificant	2 - Insignificant	3 - Partially significant	4 - Significant	5 - Very significant
f) Better management of all types of waste	1	2	3	4	5
g) Digitalization of processes in all sectors	1	2	3	4	5
h) Innovative solutions for water resource management	1	2	3	4	5
i) Promotion of production with less waste	1	2	3	4	5
j) Collaboration among government institutions, businesses, professionals and citizens	1	2	3	4	5
10. To what extent are significant the following opportunities and limitations associated with sustainability reporting?	1 - Completely insignificant	2 - Insignificant	3 - Partially significant	4 - Significant	5 - Very significant
Opportunities:					
f) Stakeholder engagement and trust building	1	2	3	4	5
g) Learning and improvement	1	2	3	4	5
h) Increasing competitiveness	1	2	3	4	5
i) Access to credit lines	1	2	3	4	5
j) Long term value creation	1	2	3	4	5
Limitations:	1	2	3	4	5
f) Lack of reporting knowledge	1	2	3	4	5
g) Lack of support programs					
h) Lack of prescribed legal and other regulations	1	2	3	4	5
i) Lack of standardization	1	2	3	4	5
j) Complexity and reporting burden	1	2	3	4	5

USE IPM

Since the questionnaire for the experts included 10 questions with five options, the fact that no options were excluded shows great consistency of this expert group, even it is composed from experts from four widening countries. This questionnaire has been used for gathering data under the Needs analysis.

By comparing the results of the Delphi study, focus groups and the needs analysis of organizations, a realistic picture will be created of the importance and opportunities for the sustainable development and sustainability reporting.